

Toward a semi-supervised learning approach to phylogenetic estimation

– Supplementary Materials –

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Supplementary tables

Table 1: Parameter of the evolutionary models. Note that base frequencies only apply to HKY and GTR models the transition-transversion ratio (Ts / Tv) only applies to the HKY model, while the instantaneous rates only apply to the GTR model. The instantaneous rates were drawn from a Dirichlet distribution and then rescaled by the last rate, which is therefore set to 1. Thus, the resulting rates are expressed as relative change compared to one fixed rate.

Parameter	Distribution
Substitution model	{JC, HKY, GTR}
Base frequencies	$\text{Dir}(\alpha, \alpha, \alpha, \alpha)$, with $\alpha = 5$
Instantaneous rates	\mathbf{r}/r_6 with $\mathbf{r} = \{r_1, \dots, r_6\} \sim \text{Dir}(\alpha, \alpha, \alpha, \alpha, \alpha, \alpha)$, and $\alpha = 5$
Ts / Tv ratio	$\mathcal{U}(2, 12)$

Table 2: Accuracy of site-specific rates estimated under different models calculated across a test set of 600 datasets generated under different modes of rate heterogeneity. The accuracy is quantified a mean squared error and as R^2 (in parenthesis), comparing the true rates with those predicted through two maximum likelihood models (gamma and free-rates) and through phyloRNN (the latter reports the same values shown in Table ??). Here, the maximum likelihood optimization was based on a fixed topology set to the true tree. Thus the maximum likelihood tree inference only optimized tree branch lengths and the parameters of the substitution model. Fixing the tree topology to the true one did not substantially improve the accuracy of the estimated rates.

Heterogeneity model	Gamma model	Free-rates	phyloRNN
All combined	0.833 (0.175)	0.709 (0.223)	0.614 (0.347)
Gamma	1.867 (0.41)	1.323 (0.619)	1.64 (0.446)
Bimodal	0.454 (0.143)	0.29 (0.146)	0.332 (0.063)
Spike-and-slab	0.538 (0.161)	0.329 (0.485)	0.517 (0.08)
Geometric Brownian	1.468 (0.339)	1.418 (0.37)	1.387 (0.268)
Codon	0.379 (0.341)	0.405 (0.313)	0.076 (0.942)
Gamma autocorrelated	1.576 (0.466)	1.612 (0.602)	0.755 (0.798)
Bimodal autocorrelated	0.329 (0.133)	0.252 (0.129)	0.178 (0.294)
Spike-and-slab autocorrelated	0.389 (0.032)	0.322 (0.032)	0.271 (0.109)
Geometric Brownian autocorrelated	0.277 (0.035)	0.272 (0.03)	0.113 (0.457)
Mixed	1.882 (0.0)	1.654 (0.0)	1.689 (0.0)

Table 3: Accuracy of total tree length estimated under different models calculated across a test set of 600 datasets generated under different modes of rate heterogeneity. The accuracy is quantified a mean absolute percentage error and as R^2 (in parentheses), comparing the true rates with those predicted through two maximum likelihood models (gamma and free-rates) and through phyloRNN (the latter reports the same values shown in Table ??). Here, the maximum likelihood optimization was based on a fixed topology set to the true tree. Thus the maximum likelihood tree inference only optimized tree branch lengths and the parameters of the substitution model. Fixing the tree topology to the true one substantially improved the accuracy of the estimated tree length.

Heterogeneity model	Gamma model	Free-rates	phyloRNN
All combined	0.106 (0.938)	0.077 (0.956)	0.152 (0.902)
Gamma	0.149 (0.976)	0.086 (0.99)	0.158 (0.902)
Bimodal	0.105 (0.935)	0.05 (0.998)	0.115 (0.953)
Spike-and-slab	0.068 (0.993)	0.064 (0.995)	0.117 (0.986)
Geometric Brownian	0.126 (0.947)	0.101 (0.931)	0.15 (0.934)
Codon	0.055 (0.999)	0.05 (0.999)	0.103 (0.971)
Gamma autocorrelated	0.147 (0.972)	0.087 (0.922)	0.173 (0.791)
Bimodal autocorrelated	0.09 (0.925)	0.057 (0.999)	0.161 (0.957)
Spike-and-slab autocorrelated	0.057 (0.995)	0.05 (0.999)	0.103 (0.971)
Geometric Brownian autocorrelated	0.06 (0.991)	0.056 (0.991)	0.177 (0.98)
Mixed	0.472 (0.605)	0.459 (0.684)	0.493 (0.6)

Table 4: Accuracy of site-specific rates estimated under different models calculated across a test set of 600 datasets generated under different modes of rate heterogeneity. Here, the phyloRNN model was re-trained with a larger proportion of mixed models in the training set to assess to what extent this could improve the estimation for this type of rate heterogeneity. Note that the accuracy values for the two maximum likelihood models are the same are reported in Table ??.

Heterogeneity model	Gamma model	Free-rates	phyloRNN
All combined	0.833 (0.175)	0.705 (0.206)	0.694 (0.209)
Gamma	1.869 (0.409)	1.311 (0.598)	1.644 (0.411)
Bimodal	0.454 (0.143)	0.28 (0.139)	0.361 (0.044)
Spike-and-slab	0.538 (0.161)	0.32 (0.484)	0.551 (0.086)
Geometric Brownian	1.469 (0.337)	1.408 (0.387)	1.415 (0.224)
Codon	0.379 (0.341)	0.405 (0.316)	0.223 (0.806)
Gamma autocorrelated	1.578 (0.465)	1.613 (0.584)	1.064 (0.66)
Bimodal autocorrelated	0.329 (0.133)	0.25 (0.112)	0.232 (0.224)
Spike-and-slab autocorrelated	0.387 (0.032)	0.323 (0.03)	0.31 (0.061)
Geometric Brownian autocorrelated	0.276 (0.034)	0.27 (0.028)	0.244 (0.207)
Mixed	1.882 (0.0)	1.656 (0.0)	1.612 (0.0)

Table 5: Accuracy of total tree length estimated under different models calculated across a test set of 600 datasets generated under different modes of rate heterogeneity. Here, the phyloRNN model was re-trained with a larger proportion of mixed models in the training set to assess to what extent that could improve the estimation of this subset of the data. the accuracy values for the two maximum likelihood models are the same are reported in Table ??.

Heterogeneity model	Gamma model	Free-rates	phyloRNN
All combined	0.106 (0.933)	0.075 (0.955)	0.196 (0.92)
Gamma	0.147 (0.977)	0.083 (0.987)	0.181 (0.958)
Bimodal	0.105 (0.936)	0.047 (0.999)	0.186 (0.941)
Spike-and-slab	0.066 (0.993)	0.055 (0.998)	0.154 (0.989)
Geometric Brownian	0.118 (0.955)	0.102 (0.929)	0.187 (0.943)
Codon	0.056 (0.999)	0.051 (0.999)	0.217 (0.942)
Gamma autocorrelated	0.156 (0.952)	0.085 (0.921)	0.224 (0.801)
Bimodal autocorrelated	0.091 (0.925)	0.057 (0.996)	0.199 (0.985)
Spike-and-slab autocorrelated	0.057 (0.995)	0.053 (0.976)	0.181 (0.977)
Geometric Brownian autocorrelated	0.055 (0.999)	0.052 (0.999)	0.187 (0.988)
Mixed	0.471 (0.605)	0.459 (0.681)	0.408 (0.798)

Table 6: Summary of 100 simulated alignments of 50 taxa and 1000 sites analyzed using RevBayes under different rate heterogeneity models. We compared the output of analyses using phyloRNN rates discretized into 4, 10, 20, and 50 rate classes against a standard gamma model. Here we report the average difference in the mean log likelihoods sampled through MCMC, as a proxy for model fit. We report the percentage of datasets resulting in equal or lower R-F distance between the estimated and the true trees and the relative improvement of weighted R-F distances (ratio between gamma and phyloRNN models). Finally, we report the improvement in the estimated total tree length.

n. partitions	Mean likelihood		R-F distance		Weighted R-F distance		Tree length error	
	Δ Lik	higher (%)	equal (%)	lower (%)	Δ wR-F	lower (%)	Δ err.	lower (%)
4	339.935	97	62	19	1.272	66	3.087	71
10	391.876	98	61	18	1.227	65	3.832	72
20	411.013	99	64	16	1.230	69	4.019	72
50	415.049	99	62	19	1.230	63	4.080	73

Table 7: Log-likelihood under the true tree. 600 simulations (rows) under different heterogeneity models and tree length. For each simulation, Log-likelihood of the simulated data is computed given the true tree, given the nucleotide matrix estimated under gamma rates, and given site-specific rates. Site-specific rates are either posteriors under gamma model, posteriors under free-rates model, estimated by phyloRNN or finally the true rates (used as input of the simulation). The full table (600 rows) is available at https://github.com/phyloRNN/Scripts_and_data

Replicate	Heterogeneity model	Tree length	LnL gamma rates	LnL free-rates	LnL phyloRNN rates	LnL true rates
0	GBM uncorrelated	0.048	-1735.990	-1735.770	-1717.994	-1735.399
1	Gamma autocorrelated	0.617	-5252.660	-5246.910	-5055.227	-5095.449
2	Bimodal uncorrelated	0.235	-2665.980	-2664.470	-2585.512	-2573.566
3	Spike-and-slab uncorrelated	0.560	-4718.620	-4713.730	-4625.221	-4686.640
4	GBM uncorrelated	0.064	-1895.890	-1877.200	-1797.892	-1800.167
5	Codon uncorrelated	1.189	-7821.070	-7817.960	-7488.423	-7497.536
6	GBM uncorrelated	16.565	-17096.470	-16919.200	-16074.284	-15844.467
7	Bimodal uncorrelated	4.568	-17651.340	-17359.680	-16690.113	-16597.409
8	Bimodal uncorrelated	2.719	-13303.310	-13201.690	-12596.996	-12568.510
9	GBM uncorrelated	3.089	-14481.340	-14437.670	-13647.083	-13678.580
10	Spike-and-slab autocorrelated	5.565	-23700.900	-23694.690	-23443.449	-23478.195
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮

Supplementary figures

Figure 1: Examples of site-specific rates (plots on the left) and their distribution (histograms on the right) based on simulations with 5,000 sites generated under different modes of rate heterogeneity : a) gamma, b) bimodal, c) spike-and-slab, d) geometric Brownian, e) codon (see Text for more details). Note that for clarity a variable number of sites are shown in the plots and the Y-axis in histogram c) is log-transformed.

Figure 2: Examples of site-specific rates (plots on the left) and their distribution (histograms on the right) based on simulations with 5,000 sites generated under different autocorrelated modes of rate heterogeneity: a) gamma, b) bimodal, c) spike-and-slab, d) geometric Brownian, e) mixed (see Text for more details). Note that for clarity the Y-axis in histograms c) and e) is log-transformed.

Figure 3: Architecture of the DL model used to infer site-specific rates and total tree length, here show for a toy example with the input being an alignment of 5 sequences of 3 sites. The shape of the input is: (n. sites = 3, n. sequences \times 4 = 20, with 4 representing the four one-hot-encoded nucleotides. The first dimension indicated with None represents the number of instances, e.g. the number of alignments in the training or test sets.

Figure 4: Training history of our DL model. The early stopping point reflects the epoch with the lowest validation loss, which combined the mean squared error of the per-site relative substitution rates and the mean squared error of the total tree length (log-transformed).

Figure 5: Examples of estimated rates (red) obtained under a maximum likelihood framework using a gamma model of rate heterogeneity. True rates are shown in blue. the estimates are shown as per-site rate (1,000 sites in each dataset) and as histograms.

Figure 6: Examples of estimated rates (red) obtained under a maximum likelihood framework using a free-rates model of rate heterogeneity. True rates are shown in blue. the estimates are shown as per-site rate (1,000 sites in each dataset) and as histograms.

Figure 7: Examples of estimated rates (red) obtained under a maximum likelihood framework using a gamma model of rate heterogeneity. True rates are shown in blue. the estimates are shown as per-site rate (1,000 sites in each dataset) and as histograms.

Figure 8: Examples of estimated rates (red) obtained under a maximum likelihood framework using a free-rates model of rate heterogeneity from datasets simulated under a mixed model (see *Methods*). True rates are shown in blue, the estimates are shown as per-site rate (1,000 sites in each dataset) and as histograms.

Figure 9: Examples of estimated rates (red) obtained under the phy1oRNN model from datasets simulated under a mixed model. True rates are shown in blue. the estimates are shown as per-site rate (1,000 sites in each dataset) and as histograms.

Figure 10: Examples of estimated rates (red) obtained under the phyLoRNN model from datasets simulated under a mixed model. True rates are shown in blue. the estimates are shown as per-site rate (1,000 sites in each dataset) and as histograms.

Figure 11: Comparison of Mean-squared error (MSE) across 600 simulations between true values and estimated values (under gamma model). MSE for the rates per site (left) and tree length (right). For each simulation, the likelihood of the true tree is compared to the likelihoods of a posterior sample of 50 trees obtained from a Bayesian analysis (GTR + gamma model). Each of 600 simulations is thus classified whether the true tree is the worst ($n=73$), inside ($n=516$) or the best ($n=11$) of the posterior sampled trees. Comparison of MSE between each pairs of class (worst, inside, best) is performed with t-test of independence. P-values accounting for Bonferroni correction; ns: $0.05 < p \leq 1$; ***: $1e-04 < p \leq 1e-03$; ****: $p \leq 1e-04$. Mean of MSE for each class (worst, inside, best) is represented as a red dot.

Figure 12: Comparison between phylogenetic inference using a gamma model of across site rate heterogeneity and fixed phyloRNN-estimated per-site rates. Boxplots summarize the results of 200 simulated datasets with 20 tips and 100 nucleotides. All analyses were carried out using RevBayes. Positive values indicate improvements in analyses using phyloRNN rates compared with gamma rates (i.e. higher sampled likelihood (a), lower distance or error between true and estimated trees (b-d)).

Figure 13: Comparison between phylogenetic inference using a gamma model of across site rate heterogeneity and fixed phyloRNN-estimated per-site rates. Boxplots summarize the results of 200 simulated datasets with 50 tips and 100 nucleotides. All analyses were carried out using RevBayes. Positive values indicate improvements in analyses using phyloRNN rates compared with gamma rates (i.e. higher sampled likelihood (a), lower distance or error between true and estimated trees (b-d)).

Figure 14: Comparison between phylogenetic inference using a gamma model of across site rate heterogeneity and fixed phyloRNN-estimated per-site rates, discretized in 4, 10, 20, and 50 rate classes, respectively. Boxplots summarize the results of 100 simulated datasets with 50 tips and 1000 nucleotides. All analyses were carried out using RevBayes. Positive values indicate improvements in analyses using phyloRNN rates compared with gamma rates (i.e. higher sampled likelihood (a), lower distance or error between true and estimated trees (b-d)). The results are shown for nine rate heterogeneity models following the order and color coding of Fig. 13.

Figure 15: Comparison between the estimated number of substitutions inferred by our phyloRNN model (y-axis) and through the *phyloP* software (phyloP nobs, x-axis) across the clownfish chromosome 1. We calculated here the estimated number of substitutions along the 26-species phylogeny of clownfish across blocks of 10, 100, 500, and 1000 sites, as the sum of the site-specific estimated number of substitutions. Our results show that there is an increasingly strong correlation between estimates as we increase the number of sites considered.